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Editor

Prof. Dr.M. Manimohan (Rtd)

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.m.manimohan@gmail.com

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Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

drsasikumar@gmail.com

Managing Editor

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dr.g.narayanan@gmail.com

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jichelnu@gmail.com

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Thematic and Psychological Aspects of the Curses in the light of the *Mahābhārata*- An Analysis.

Pratiksha Goswami¹

Abstract

If the story of the human civilization has been observed, the two most prominent emotions that dominates human minds are happiness and sorrow. Though there are some other emotional aspects of human mind, these two can be bluntly visible by anyone in the human world irrespective of any epithets and qualifications. The story of human civilization adjoints boons and curses respectively with happiness and sorrow from time immemorial. Irrespective of geographical boundary, the literary documents of the whole world showcase boons and curses and their reflections in the society, corroborating human happiness and sorrow respectively in various directions. The present paper aims at dealing with the thematic and psychological aspects of the curses in the light of the *Mahābhārata*. It will try to ascertain those from the perspective of modern outlook and theories.

Key Words: Mahābhārata, theme, psychological, curses and cause-and -effect relationship.

Scope:

- To access the thematic importance of the curses in the light of the *Mahābhārata*.
- To access the psychological aspects of the curses of the *Mahābhārata*.
- To determine the cause-and-effect relationship of the curses into the storyline of the *Mahābhārata*.

Methodology

The methodology of this proposed work will be basically narrative and explanatory. In some portions there will also be analysis on the

1 Research Scholar, Gauhati University, Guwahati-14

basis of a comparative discourse.

Key Findings: To find out how curses of the *Mahābhārata* are related to the psychic state of the curse giver and curse receiver. This also tries to locate how these curses add impetus in the forward journey of the storyline.

Introduction

The story of human civilization provides the two most prominent emotions that remained strong in human minds from the beginning of the human civilization which are happiness and sorrow. Though there are some other emotional aspects of human mind and these are expressed in various situation of life but the feeling of happiness and sorrow remains prominent irrespective in any stage or status of the human being. The story of human civilization also adjoints boons and curses respectively with happiness and sorrow from time immemorial. So, the curses are related with the sorrow of the human mind. The main idea of curse is of inflicting punishment or even destruction on a person who had done wrong. The Sanskrit rendering of curse is *śāpa*. The word *śāpa* is derived from the root *Śap* which refers to vengeance. It is stated in Grammar as *Śāpa Ākrośe (Dikshita 233,260)*. The term *ākrosa* means assailing with harsh language, scolding, reviling and abuse (Williams 128). *Ākrosa* also means curse, imprecation and oath (Apte 309). Monier Williams gives several meanings to *śāpa* viz., curse, malediction, abuse, oath, imprecation, ban and interdiction (1065). According to the *Oxford English Dictionary* the curse is an utterance consigning or supposed or intended to consign a person or a thing to spiritual or temporal evil, the vengeance of the deity, basting of malignant fate etc (Simpson 331). The word *śāpa* and its root form *śap* occur in the *R̥gveda* with its traditional meaning; i.e., the infliction of punishment in one place (*R̥gveda*, 1.41.8). The *Taittiriyasamhitā* mentions the story of curse given to a fish by the god Agni. Agni had three brothers. They perished while carrying the offering to the gods. Agni was afraid of the thought the same misfortune would fall on him. So, he ran away and entered into the waters. The gods came to search for him as they needed him for sacrifice. The fish told the gods about Agni's presence in water. So, Agni cursed the fish and said that humans would take fish as their food (Taiteriyā Samhitā,

2.6.6.1). These Vedic texts mention curses, but it is important to note that Vedic texts are not full of such occurrences. Whereas, the Epics and Purāṇas have used the strategy of curse on various accounts. Interestingly, the beginning of Rāmāyaṇa is based on such an incident. It is known to all that Vālmīki cursed *vyādha*, when the latter was seen as the killer of the Krauñca bird in the *Rāmāyaṇa* making the other bird companion-less (Rāmāyaṇa, 2.15). The curse coming out of the mouth of Vālmīki has been treated as the example of first ornate poem of Sanskrit literature. Like these works, a great chunk of the *Mahābhārata* story has been seen to be regulated by curse and its impact. Apparently, the curses are associated with negative environment, but the *Mahābhārata* story, in many places, establishes that the curses even sometimes remain the knot for binding the two points of an incident. It connects the anecdotes in many places. It is obvious that whatever be the substratum of the curse, it is somehow connected to a human being remaining behind the locus. This reflects the view that curses are always connected to the mind of a living being and is somehow affects human society. Thus, the curse giver, the receiver of the curse and the volume of the curse create a special type of formula in the surroundings of happenings with their force to integrate customized events. Therefore, a curse may be connected with three primary domains or aspects viz., social, practical and psychological. In the present academic venture, the psychological aspects of the curses of the Ādiparvan and the Vanaparvan of the *Mahābhārata* have been taken as the field of study.

The Curses of the *Mahābhārata* can be divided in the following manner:

- Curses connected to Sacrifices.
- Curses connected to the Births of Low Caste.
- Curses connected to Birth of Offsprings.
- Curse; that is used for Prevention of Criticism.
- Curses that turn into Boons.

These divisions can be established through the explanations of various dimensions that are connected directly or indirectly with the curse. This is discussed here one by one.

Curses connected to Sacrifices: In the storyline of the *Mahābhārata* there are various accounts of the sacrificial rites can be found. Those sacrificial rites are performed to gain something. These sacrificial rites held an important place in the *Mahābhārata*. Some curses in the *Mahābhārata* are related to the sacrificial rites. As for example,

a.(i). The Sacrifice of Janamejaya: Vedavyāsa started the story of the *Mahābhārata* in the Ādiparvan with the narration of the Janamejaya's serpent sacrifice. In connection with the story Janamejaya's serpent sacrifice two curses two curses have been shown in the epic story; one is Kadrū's curse to her sons and another is the curse of the sage Śṛṅgī towards Parikṣit.

The sage Kaśyapa had two wives; one was Vinatā and the other was Kadrū. From the sage Kaśyapa Vinatā had two sons named Aruṇa and Garuḍa. On the other hand, Kadrū had one thousand snakes as her sons (Mahābhārata, 1.16.6 -1.16.9). Once Vinatā and Kadrū argued on the topic of the colour of the tail of Uccaiḥśravā. Uccaiḥśravā was a horse who was emerged from the ocean as a result of churning of the ocean of deities and demons (MB 1.18.37). Vinatā said that the colour of Uccaiḥśravā was white, so the tail of the Uccaiḥśravā had to be white, but Kadrū argued with her that the colour of the tail of Uccaiḥśravā was black. Actually, that was not the case. Then they put a condition that the winner of this debate would be the master and the loser would be the servant (MB-1.20.1-4). Actually, the colour of the tail of Uccaiḥśravā was white. But to win the argument Kadrū ordered her sons to cover the tail of Uccaiḥśravā with their body to make it black so that she became the winner, but her sons rebelled against her. Therefore, she cursed her sons that they would be offered to Agni in Janamejaya's serpent sacrifice (MB 1.20.6-8). Another curse connected to Janamejaya's serpent sacrifice was the curse of the sage Śṛṅgī towards Parikṣit. Once the king Parikṣit, the son of Abhimanyu went for hunting and wounded a deer. To search for that wounded deer the king entered the hermitage of the sage Śamīka and asked for the deer, but Śamīka was engaged in meditation. Therefore, he was not aware of the outer world. So, he didn't respond to the king (MB 1.40.19-20). Insulted by that the king Parikṣit misbehaved with the sage by putting a dead snake around his neck and left from there (MB 1.40.21). After a while, the sage Śṛṅgī, the son of the sage

Śamīka arrived near him and saw him in that miserable state. After hearing from Kṛṣṇa that the king Parīkṣit was guilty of his father he could not control his anger and cursed him that he would be killed by the snake called Takṣaka within seven days (MB 1.41.12). On the other hand, Takṣaka was glad to receive this opportunity to avenge his family who were burnt alive at the forest of Khāṇḍava by Arjuna, the grandfather of Parīkṣit (MB 1.226.5). After knowing the story of the death of his father, Janamejaya determined to kill all the snakes. So, he prepared the serpent sacrifice (MB 1.51.6 -9). In this storyline these two curses are seen to create the base for Janamejaya's serpent sacrifice. Kadrū's curse her children helped Janamejaya to stay away from bad name when he killed thousands of innocent snakes just for his revenge. On the other hand, by the curse of the sage Śṛṅgi, Takṣaka the king of snake got the chance to complete his revenge on the lineage of Pāṇḍavas for the misdeed of Arjuna. These two curses have prepared the base for future actions of Janamejaya. Thus, these two curses are insinuated in the story to give a great start of the whole epic.

Curses Connected to Low Births: Many curses are seen to be related with the birth of low caste people in the *Mahābhārata*. Following are some of the examples in this regard.

b.(i). The Birth of Vidura: In the *Mahābhārata*, Vedavyāsa had always created a background story for all the characters who was dealing with the storyline of the *Mahābhārata*. Likewise, Vedavyāsa had also created a background story for the character Vidura to justify his knowledge despite being a low caste person. Once the sage Aṇīmāṇḍavya was wrongly accused of stealing and he was hanged as his punishment. After his death, he confronted Dharma that though he had killed the child of the bird still his punishment was severe for his deed because he did a long penance to compensate his bad deed. Therefore, to give him such a terrible death Dharma would have to face the consequences. The sage Aṇīmāṇḍavya cursed him to get his birth in a family of low caste. Therefore, Dharma was born as Vidura, the brother of Pāṇḍu and Dhṛtarāstra from the low caste mother (MB 1.63.92-97). This curse also bears a social angle. Here Vedavyāsa wants to convey the message to people that law stands above all powers. So, even being the strong king, Dharma could not

do anything to lessen the curse of Aṅīmāṇḍavya. Another lesson that this incident of curse imparts that a curse should be in a proper proportion with that of the wrong deed. Otherwise, the curse giver may again face the negative consequence his wrong decision. The *Mahābhārata* has also projects a detail report on various types of punishments many of which are connected with incidents of curse. In this regard there is a detailed discussion on punishment in the *Arthaśāstra* of Kautilya (*Arthaśāstra*, 1.4.11-14).

3) Curses Connected to Birth of Offsprings: In the *Mahābhārata* it can be seen that some births are related with the curses or boons. Following are the examples of the curses which are related with births of various characters in the epic.

3.A. The Birth of Bhīṣma: To create the base of the birth of Bhīṣma, Vedavyāsa has inserted two curses viz., the curse of Brahmā on Mahābhiṣa and the curse of the sage Vaśiṣṭha to the eight Vasus. Once there was a gathering with the lord Brahmā where all gods were present including the king Mahābhiṣa. In that gathering suddenly Gaṅgā entered and because of the wind she got undressed. In that situation everyone closed their eyes except the king Mahābhiṣa. He started looking at her with full of desires. Then Brahmā cursed Mahābhiṣa for his wrongful attitude to Gaṅgā by saying that he would be born again at earth and deceived by Gaṅgā for whom he possessed strong desires (1.96.3 -7), that Mahābhiṣa was the king Śāntanu with whom Gaṅgā got married conditionally.

Again, there was a curse from the sage Vaśiṣṭha to the eight Vasus which was interconnected with the birth of the great Bhīṣma. Once the eight Vasus with their wives visited the hermitage of Vaśiṣṭha. On the request of the wife of Dyau-one of the eight Vasus, the Vasus stole the auspicious cow called Nandinī belonging to the sage Vaśiṣṭha from his hermitage (MB 1.99.26 -28). As the sage Vaśiṣṭha came to know that the Vasus stole his auspicious cow, he immediately cursed the Vasus to be born as humans in the earth (MB 1.99.31 -32). When they got to know about the curse, they pleaded Vaśiṣṭha to lessen the load of the curse. Accordingly, the sage told them that the seven Vasus would have been rescued at the beginning of their births from the human world, but there was one Vasu who was really guilty called Dyau. So, he had to live his life as human. He would

live his life as a great warrior with no wife and children (MB 1.99.38-41). When the last time comes, he could escape from his human birth. Then the Vasus requested Gaṅgā to bear them as her children and release them at their births (MB1.96.15-16). Therefore, Gaṅgā married to the king Śāntanu who was actually the king Mahābhīṣa in earlier birth and was cursed by Brahmā. When she got married to Śāntanu she put a condition that the king should never ask her any question about her deeds (MB 1.98.3). Whenever he would ask her a single question, she would leave him (MB 1.98.4). The king accepted it. Then she got pregnant by him and one by one seven times she sacrificed their children to the water (MB1.98.13), but when the eighth one took birth the king Śāntanu could not control him and stopped her from her insane deed (1.98.15). In this situation, under their contract, Gaṅgā left the king and told him about the story of Vasus. The child who was saved by the king was the eighth Vasu of the previous birth called Dyau and Gaṅgā took him to prepare him for the throne and promised the king to return the child when the time would come (1.99.46). This child was named Bhīṣma later on who became the great warrior in the *Mahābhārata*. By this way these two curses are interconnected with each other and made the perfect joint for the storyline in connection with the birth of Bhīṣma which is one of the great anecdotes that takes the story of the *Mahābhārata* forward.

3.B. Birth of the Pāṇḍavas: It has already been discussed that Vedavyāsa had always created a background story for all the characters that take part in the story of the epic. Similarly, there remains a story in the background of the birth of the Pāṇḍavas where the curse to the king Pāṇḍu remains as a key point. Pāṇḍu was the king of Hastināpura and he had two wives viz., Kuntī and Mādri. Once the king with two wives went for hunting in the forest. Then on the request of Mādri he threw an arrow to a deer who was actually the sage Kindama. The sage Kindama was in a form of deer and was with his wife at that time (1.95.59). Therefore, the sage Kindama cursed Pāṇḍu that he would face his death whenever he would try to be intimate with his wife (MB 1.95.60). By adding this incident in the story of the *Mahābhārata* Vedavyāsa made sure to bring an extraordinary birth to the Pāṇḍavas to show their immense strength

and to make a way to fulfil the boon of Kuntī which she received from the sage Durvāsā that she could bear the children of gods (MB 1.67.135).

4) Curse; that is used for Prevention of Criticism: Many curses have been inserted in the *Mahābhārata* to save a character from any kind of criticism in the storyline of the Epic. Some of these types are listed here.

4.A. Curse of Duryodhana: In the Vanaparvan, Vedavyāsa has inserted the curse from the sage Maitreya to Duryodhana to create a base for the fight between Duryodhana and Bhīmasena. When Bhīmasena broke the thigh of Duryodhana which was against the rules of the fight with mace, to protect the character of Bhīmasena from any blemish Vedavyāsa inserted the curse of the sage Maitreya to Duryodhana. Duryodhana once insulted the sage Maitreya and as a result of that the sage cursed Duryodhana by saying that for him a great war would happen and, in that war, Bhīmasena would break his thigh with a blow of his mace (MB 3.10.34). This curse was inserted for the destruction of Duryodhana and to protect the character of Bhīma from his wrong decision to attack Duryodhana in his thigh.

5) Curses that turn into Boons: The *Mahābhārata* story shows that many of the curses are seen to take the strength of boons with the passage of time and the context of the happenings. Some of these are-

5.A. Curse of Urvaśī to Arjuna: In various scenes of the *Mahābhārata*, curses sometimes appear as boons in reality. Many incidents of curses turn into boons at different point of time for the recipient of the particular curse. This development also bears deep significance in the whole story. In this account, the curse of Arjuna received by Urvaśī can be stated. During Arjuna's visit to his biological father Indra in the heavenly abode, a celestial nymph named Urvaśī was romantically attracted towards him. His bravery and virility swept her off her feet, but her sexual advance was repelled by Arjuna. He gave accounts of her associations with his forefathers and addressed her as mother, thus, he refused to accept the request of Urvaśī (MB 3.46.46-47). Being rejected by Arjuna, Urvaśī felt humiliated and cursed him to be a eunuch (MB 3.46.49-50), but Indra- the biological father of Arjuna changed the time period for

this curse into a year which he could use in his thirteenth year of exile (MB 3.46.56-58).

Here, actually the curse given to Arjuna became a boon for him and it helped him to complete his task at the thirteenth year of his exile. No one could think that the mighty warrior Arjuna would disguise himself in the form of a eunuch who could sing and dance among women. Actually, this incident has put an impetus to create a sense of allegory to the story, thus it reminds of Plato's theory of allegory. The meaning of allegory is to reveal the hidden meaning of any picture, poem or story or any other thing. An allegorical writing is the type of writing having two levels of meaning. A literary meaning is the content or the subject matter and allegorical meaning is the symbolic or metaphorical suggestion. In this incident though Arjuna becomes a eunuch but his true identity was covered and in the inner level he was not the individual which has been shown in the story.

The cause and effect of these curses in the storyline can be shown in the following table.

Parva	Adhyāya	who	To whom	Cause	Effect
Ādi	Āstika	Kadru	her sons	Because they did not follow her orders.	In Janamejaya's serpent sacrifice the snakes were sacrificed in the Āstikaparvan(Ādiparvan)
Ādi	Āstika	Śṛṅgī	king Parikṣit.	Because the king insulted the Sage's father.	Takṣaka killed Parikṣit in the Āstikaparvan (Ādiparvan)
Ādi	Sambha	Aṇī māṇḍavya	Dharmarāja.	Because of the Dharmarāja's wrongful decision.	Dharma took birth as Vidura in the Sambhavarva(Ādiparvan)

Ādi	Sambhava	Kindama	Pāṇḍu	Because he killed the sage and his wife while the sage was with his wife in an intimate situation.	Pāṇḍu could not be the father of his children in the Sambhavarva (Ādiparvan)
Ādi	Sambha	Vaśiṣṭha	the Vasus	Because they stole the auspicious cow of the Vaśiṣṭha.	Vasus took birth as human in the Sambhavaparva (Ādiparvan)
Ādi	Sambha	Brahmā	Mahābhiṣa	Because of the wrongful stare of him towards Gaṅgā.	Mahābhiṣa took birth as king Śāntanu in the Sambhavaparva (Ādiparvan)
Vana	Aranya	Maitreya	Duryodhana	Because he insulted the sage's words.	Duryodhana got killed by Bhīma in the Gadāyud-dhaparvan. (Śalya Parvan)
Vana	Indra lokābhigamana	Urvaśī	Arjuna	Because Arjuna refused the proposal of Urvaśī.	Arjuna took form of a eunuch in the Pāṇḍava praveśaparvan (Vanaparvan)

These curses bear a strong psychological base in the epic story. It is true that the curses are the result of anger and agony. Anger is the prominent emotion of the human mind which has psychological base. Psychology is the scientific study of the behaviour and mental processes of the human being. Behaviour includes all of our outward or overt actions and reactions viz., the verbal and facial expressions

and movements. Mental processes refer to all the internal and covert activity of one's mind, such as, thinking, feeling and remembering. It is a scientific study because to study behaviour and mental processes, the psychologists use the scientific methods for understanding more precisely and accurately. The term *psychology* has its origin from two Greek words *psyche* and *logos*. *Psyche* refers to soul and *logos* means study. Thus, literally the term *psychology* means the study of soul or science of soul. According to William McDougall, Psychology is a science which aims to give us better understanding and control of the behavior of the organism as a whole (McDougall 38). The subject matter of Psychology is affect, behaviour and cognition. The affect for Psychology is the actual mental processes that makes up moods, feelings, and emotional state. An example for affect would be feeling sad about something happening. Behaviour includes the actual actions and responses of organisms. Behaviour can include the way one acts in any given situation. Cognition is actual mental events and the processes that result from those. This can be related with the above-mentioned curses also. As for example, in Pāṇḍu's curse it can be stated that the affect remains as the anger and the disturbance felt by the sage in his inner mind. The term *behaviour* can be connected to the action of the curse giver by the sage to Pāṇḍu. Cognition refers to the negative happenings in the mind of sage as well as the curse itself. In this situation one extra point can be added. It is the outcome of the curse which actually remained very important regarding the events of the *Mahābhārata*. Here the outcome is that Pāṇḍu could never be the father of his own child.

It has been stated that anger works as a stimulating event for curses. Traditionally Psychology explained anger as a phase of the instinct of pugnacity- a conception of an innate, heredity impulse to fight, attack and destroy (Stagner 110). This anger is connected to various stages of mental condition. Psychologists divided anger into five stages (Puff 20). Through these five stages of the anger, the curse of Śṛṅgī to Parīkṣit and the curse of Vaśiṣṭha to the eight Vasus can be evaluated. These five stages are as follows-

Getting Triggered: Anger always has a trigger point which could be external or internal. External triggers include life events, hurtful remarks from others etc. Internal triggers of anger could be one's

thoughts and feelings (Puff 20). In these two curses the external trigger for the sage Śṛṅgī is the dishonorable deed of Parīkṣit. Again, for the sage Vaśiṣṭha the external trigger is the stealing of his cow.

Build Up Anger: After getting triggered, the mind tells a story of why the anger is justified and when this happens anger starts to get a momentum inside the mind (Puff). In these two examples the sage Śṛṅgī and the sage Vaśiṣṭha got triggered by the king Parīkṣit's behaviour and it can be said that they took those incidents as the justification of their anger and thus their anger started to blow high.

Preparation for Action: Once the anger reaches a certain threshold the body starts preparation for action (Puff), thus, the body of the sage Vaśiṣṭha and Śṛṅgī had prepared for future action.

Feeling the Impulse to Act: It can be said that when the body of the two sages had prepared themselves for action, their mind pushed their body to act on that feeling.

Acting on that Anger: It is true that the energy that is built up always seeks quick release. It can be said that the sages Śṛṅgī Vaśiṣṭha could not control themselves and cursed the king Parīkṣit and the eight Vasus subsequently in that way.

It is important to note that in the *Mahābhārata* story the locus of a curse does not appear to be limited to any caste or a particular community. Even the most valorous person may be cursed and even the sages are also seen to be cursed. The curses of the *Mahābhārata* can be illustrated through the modern perspectives of the theory of emotion. Emotion refers to complex reactions consisting of (a) psychological responses such as changes in blood pressure and heart rate; (b) the subjective feelings which describe as happiness, anger, sorrow, disgust and so on; and (c) expressive reactions that reflect these internal states; such as, changes in facial expressions and postures (Baron 317). In 1962, Sachter and Singer gave cognitive arousal theory of emotion in which both the physical arousal and the labelling of that arousal based on cues from the environment must occur before the emotion is experienced (Ciccarelli 383). In their cognitive arousal theory, Sachter and Singer proposed that two things have to happen before emotion occurs the physical arousal and a labelling of the arousal based on cues from the surrounding environment. These two things happen at the same time, resulting

in the labelling of the emotion. In this theory, a stimulus leads to both bodily arousal and the labelling of that arousal, based on the surrounding context which leads to the experience and labelling of the emotional reaction. For example, if a person comes across a snarling dog while taking a walk, the physical arousal is accompanied by the thought or cognition that this must be fear. Then and only then will the person experience the sense of fear (Baron 338). It is given clearly in this context.

Stimulus	First response	Second Response	Effect
Snarling dog	Cognitive appraisal	Conscious fear	Arousal changes in body

By this theory the above-mentioned curses can be revisited. The curse of Pāṇḍu can also be examined through this theory of emotion of Sachter and Singer. In connection with Kindama's curse to Pāṇḍu the stimulus was Pāṇḍu's impulsive act of throwing an arrow to the sage Kindama. The first responses for the sage Kindama were physiological arousals like his body got hurt (MB 1.96.59). This is referred in the *Mahābhārata* story. Here the word tells that he was physically injured. Then the sage Kindama noticed the cue of the environment in his surrounding which can be correlated with the suggestion given in the Sachter and Singer's theory of emotion. Finally getting triggered by the anger the sage Kindama cursed Pāṇḍu in that way.

Again, the curse of Maitreya to Duryodhana is also the result of the anger of the sage Maitreya. When Duryodhana disrespected the sage and did not listen to his words that triggered the sage Maitreya. It can be pointed out as the external trigger point between Duryodhana and sage Maitreya. The insult of Duryodhana was the stimulus for the sage. After getting triggered by the anger, his eyes turned red because of anger (MB 3.10.32). Thereafter, his mind pushed him to do some action and influenced by that emotion he cursed Duryodhana to be the cause of the great war and in that war, Bhīma would break his thigh with a blow of his mace (MB 3.10.34).

Similarly, the curse of Urvaśī to Arjuna is also the result of anger. When Arjuna rejected Urvaśī's offer because she was related to his

forefathers (MB 3.46.46), Urvaśī got offended by his behaviour. On the basis of Sachter and Singer's theory of emotion the story of Urvaśī and Arjuna can be projected. Here, the stimulus for Urvaśī was the rejection of Arjuna. The first responses were the physiological arousals; such as her body got tensed and breathing rate increased (MB 3.46.48). Then she noticed the cue of the environment which was the rejection of Arjuna to her proposal made her feel the emotion of anger thus, it can be stated that getting triggered by anger she cursed Arjuna in that way.

Therefore, there is no harm in saying that curses are mainly an outburst of anger caused by agony, cheating or wrongdoings and a person curses only when the curse giver is troubled to an extreme level by the recipients. These curses were used to deliver the decisions. During the time of the *Mahābhārata* when someone was cursed, it was established that the recipient was guilty of something and no one would raise a question about that. The curses are the result of utterance of speech. These speeches are divided into two in the Speech Act Theory of J.L. Austin. According to J.L. Austin there are two types of speech namely constative and performative. The constative type is a type of speech which can be determined to be true or false or denotes action. Performative speeches indicate the action which the speeches perform themselves by uttering words. These speeches do not dictate something. They produce affects which can be seen later on (Austin 5). J.L. Austin provides examples of performative speech viz., marriage, vows, apologies and naming of things. They are not merely describing an action but creating the action through the speech. Aligning with Austin's stipulation for performative speech, a curse is not the act of describing or reporting on something but it is being created its effects through language. Curses have the power to shape or alter the destinies of those they are uttered against. As for example, the curse of the sage Kindama altered the lives of Pāṇḍu, Kuntī, Mādrī and most importantly the lives of the Pāṇḍavas in the *Mahābhārata*.

Conclusion

It can be stated that curses play an important role in *Mahābhārata* to bind the knots of the two stories. These curses have psychological effects. Curses are the result of the negative happenings in the

mind of the curse giver. These negative happenings are based on the surrounding environments and absolute trigger points being influenced by the trigger points and surrounding environments the curse giver pronounces the curse to the recipient. The curses of the *Mahābhārata*, can also be projected on the basis of the the modern theory of emotion. Emotions are the cause of any actions of human being. So, these emotions of curse giver play important role in the process of uttering a curse. In the *Mahābhārata* all these curses work as effective strategies to place the whole story in a lucid manner. So that the reader can get the impact without any hindrance. This side of the curse can be the base to call Vedavyāsa is a psychotherapist.

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